

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the exports of Russian companies under sanctions pressure is relevant because Western sanctions imposed in response to various political events significantly impacted multiple sectors of the Russian economy. Analyzing exports allows us to assess which sectors suffered the most and which were able to adapt or find new markets. With limited access to traditional markets such as the European Union and the United States, Russian companies are increasingly finding new customers in Asia, Africa and Latin America. Export analysis helps identify potentially attractive markets and industries. Overall, analyzing the exports of Russian companies under sanctions pressure allows not only assessing the current situation but also developing strategies for sustainable growth and adaptation to changing conditions.

Literature review

As known, sanctions against the Russian Federation began to be imposed in 2014 against the backdrop of the events related to the annexation of Crimea to Russia and the conflict in Eastern Ukraine.

As noted by I. N. Timofeev, the UK is one of the key initiators of sanctions against Russia. The author suggests that the UK applies sanctions less actively than the US or the EU but uses them much more actively than China and Russia. Russia is becoming a priority target for London in terms of the number of sanctions imposed and the variety of methods used [1].

According to V. V. Voynikov unilateral EU sanctions, contrary to their purpose, are designed to punish Russia by inflicting maximum damage. The author believes that a number of restrictive measures taken by the EU against the Russian Federation go beyond the authorizations established by international law. This is especially true for the measures adopted in 2022. Moreover, applying the adopted restrictive measures is becoming increasingly sophisticated, which indicates that the European Union and its individual members are abusing their position [2].

T. Yamada shows that, in general, states imposing sanctions do not intend to rely on countermeasures (third parties) to justify their measures. Thus, sanctions against Russia are not considered a practice that can contribute to the creation of a rule on third party countermeasures; in other words, the practice negatively affects the issue of third party countermeasures [3].

The sanctions significantly impacted Russia economically, energetically, politically, and long-term. Their effectiveness in the long term is a matter of debate and depends on various factors including domestic politics and international relations.

O. Latipov et al. using a sectoral partial equilibrium model estimate the effects of sanctions imposed by the United States and the European Union. According to the authors, they will lead to welfare losses in Russia of at least 996 million dollars per year, which will cost EU consumers 150 million dollars. Tariff sanctions imposed by the U.S. will lead to large welfare losses for Russia and significant inefficiencies for the EU [4].

According to J. Walterskirchen, sanctions against Russia after the annexation of Crimea did not achieve their goal, which became evident after the military escalation in February 2022 [5].

Y. A. Shcherbanin considers some results of the Russian cargo transportation obtained nine years after the announcement of economic sanctions against Russian individuals and entities. It is noted that their imposition reflects the complete non-compliance with WTO principles, particularly the provisions of GATT and GATS, and the refusal of the WTO to fulfill its direct responsibilities. By the middle of 2022, the volume of cargo transportation recovered, and in early 2023, the volume of Russian transportation increased markedly [6].

E. B. Lenchuk found that bilateral economic sanctions imposed in 2014 negatively impacted both outward and inward FDI activity among genuine investors. The authors show that the expansion of economic ties through the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) facilitated FDI inflows to Russia [7].

According to S. A. Afontsev, the escalation of economic sanctions against the Russian Federation cannot shift the country's foreign policy in the direction preferred by the sending countries. On the contrary, higher sanctions costs for the Russian economy fuel domestic political support for current foreign policy decisions. Conflict resolution should rely on multilateral political dialog rather than economic sanctions [8].

P. Alexander et al. write that the rise in food prices caused by restrictions on exports from Russia and Ukraine is exacerbated by rising energy prices, which increases the costs of agricultural inputs such as fertilizers. Reduced land use intensification caused by higher input costs will lead to expansion of agricultural land and the associated loss of carbon and biodiversity [9].

S. V. Zhukov et al. conclude that the possibility of increasing exports for post-Soviet oil exporters is relatively limited. The authors believe that oil exporters from the Persian Gulf countries win in this situation. To ensure the sustainability of economic growth, Russia and Kazakhstan need to diversify export goods, which requires the creation of modern production facilities [10].

C. Rühl analyzes the sanctions against Russia about the oil and gas sector. The author shows that the risk that tougher sanctions can turn against the sanctioning countries themselves and damage their economies is manageable [11].

According to M. A. Makushin⁶ Russia may underdeliver 49.35 million tons of coal to the EU (22% of Russian coal exports in 2021), equivalent to 3.84 billion USD. According to the author, three main scenarios of interaction between the Russian and world coal markets are possible: inertial (maintaining the share of European countries in the actual structure of supplies through agreements with Turkish traders), transformational (complete switch of supplies to new markets), and inertial-transformational (gradual replacement of the European market by the Asian and new markets in Africa and America) [12].

Notably, the sanctions did not pass without a trace – they led to problems in various spheres of the economy and society in Russia, creating serious challenges for the government and the population.

A.N. Semin et al. write that metallurgists faced a significant increase in logistics costs. The cost of freight transportation from Nakhodka to China has increased 2-2.5 times. At the same time, the ports of Primorsky Krai are physically unable to handle all export cargoes from Russia to Asia. It is necessary to expand the capacity of the BAM and Trans-Siberian railroad lines. Because of this, metallurgical companies are forced to send cargoes to Asia via Black Sea ports, where freight also increased 2-3 times due to risks for shipping. As a result of the cessation of imports from Europe and North America, the cost of procurement and delivery of basic auxiliary materials: electrodes, ferroalloys, refractories, rolls increased significantly [13].

E. B. Lenchuk showed that overcoming critical import dependence in the high-tech sphere is a priority task, the solution of which requires mobilization of the country's efforts in scientific and technological development. The author presents proposals on the main directions of state policy aimed to overcome technological dependence, accelerate technological modernization in Russia, and mobilize scientific and technological potential for developing and implementing key breakthrough technologies [14].

Thus, the scientific problem of reorienting Russian companies' exports under sanctions is the need for comprehensive analysis and the development of strategies that will help them adapt to the changing conditions of foreign trade.

The main aspects of this problem include identification of new markets, diversification of export structure, cross-cultural aspects, development of new business models, risk management, government support, innovation and adaptation of production. These aspects emphasize the complexity and diversity of problems faced by Russian companies in export reorientation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used were articles from periodical scientific journals: Herald of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Intereconomics, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Comparative Economic Studies, Nature Food, International Economics and Economic Policy, Geography and Natural Resources, Steel in Translation.

The methods used in the article were: case study (to analyze successful and unsuccessful export reorientation strategies of other countries or companies) and SWOT analysis (assessment of strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats related to export reorientation).

RESULTS

Before deciding to enter the international market, an entrepreneur needs to analyze the state of the business, assess the export potential of the company and answer several important questions for the success of their business:

1. Are the company's products in steady demand in the Russian market, and how can the sanctions be imposed on the company's ability to gain a foothold in the global market segment because of the reference to Russian origin?
2. Is the domestic market's potential exhausted and ready to invest in the risks of further sanctions waves against Russian enterprises abroad?
3. Does the company have a sufficient financial cushion to enter the foreign market, and where to get new cheap money in case of recession or force majeure effects of sanctions attacks and vessels on any products from Russia, as well as in case of Russia's withdrawal from the WTO?
4. Is the entrepreneur ready to organize 'from scratch' the export structure of their products, what sales channels they prepared for exporting them outside Russia, and what is the logistical risk and currency risk, the possibility of non-payment in currency by foreign buyers?
5. How competitive are the products that the company plans to export and how can the supplier guarantee its demand given the existing problem with component and element base, which the sanctions impact intensified?
6. What steps are planned to be taken to enter the international market, whether the institution of local intermediaries is taken into account, and what is the assistance of local CCI and Internet resources that guarantee qualitative and objective presentation of information about the goods supplied from Russia abroad?

Only after answering all the above questions and assessing the risks we can move to concrete actions, realizing the high volatility and conjuncture of global markets and the forthcoming sanctions from other countries in various business sectors against Russia.

The first thing to do is to draw up an algorithm of clear sequential actions. A well-developed plan will allow avoiding the mistakes common to newcomer companies in the international market.

The following tentative list of activities can be taken as a basis:

1. Identify the target segment and focus group of potential consumers of Russian goods and the local disposition of Russian export goods in global markets.

When selecting a market for Russian exports, it is necessary to consider not only marketing data but also the nuances of the legislation of importing countries, customs peculiarities of clearance and the conjuncture of market relations within the target market. Special attention should be paid to import restrictions and taxation peculiarities, WTO baskets and hidden protectionism, localized production of similar goods in the importing country, and cultural, ethnic, social, and religious differences.

2. Determining the depth of the market strata and finding a potential buyer, working with them and their motivation to buy.

The choice of a successful and unique trade strategy will depend on the characteristics of the products to be exported, the priorities set and ranked, the desired market dominance, profit maximization and a number of other factors. The products can be sold through wholesale or artificially initiated sales channels or through opening a representative office and organizing a local dealer network, based on the institution of intermediaries or local business representatives of SROs and CClIs, attracted as a 'soft' and 'smart' force.

3. Creation of sales channels and delivery to the potential consumer: logistics, insurance, turnkey corporate support, options for upgrades and local repairs of the brand representative's corporate style.

Even at the planning stage, it is necessary to determine the type of transportation, choose the most profitable ways of delivery of goods, and the storage conditions. In addition, it is necessary to study in detail the peculiarities of crossing the Russian border and the customs requirements and wishes of the importing country, to take into account the collapsed channels of pre-sanctions commodity exchange and the possible negative consequences of the delivery of goods by any type of transportation by logisticians from Russia.

4. Financial schemes to pay for cargoes from Russia through traditional means of payment and cryptocurrencies.

According to the Russian Federation's legislation, foreign economic transactions worth over five thousand USD are subject to mandatory registration. You can find out the terms of

the procedure directly from the servicing bank or credit organization, contact a factoring or investment group, and which amount of foreign currency proceeds will again be mandatory for sale at a fixed market rate, in case of prolongation of the Ukrainian conflict and weakening of the official rate of the Russian ruble.

Customs policy in the WTO and peculiarities of Russian exports in the conditions of sanctions confrontation: peculiarities of the US and European sanctions packages.

According to the existing codes and list of TN VED, trade procedures of international legislation, when goods pass through the state border, the exporter needs to undergo the customs clearance procedure and bring it to the global level of INCOTERMS-2020 requirements, pay the required duties and customs fees. Export clearance is governed by the Customs Code of the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU Customs Code) and harmonized in the EEC regulations.

Customs clearance of goods for export includes the following activities:

- Providing a complete description and title documents for the goods to customs officials. The essence of presenting the goods is to notify the controlling authorities of their arrival; the actual presentation takes place at the request of customs representatives.
- Declaring the cargo and determining its actual 'invoice' value. Before the cargo leaves the territory of the country, the exporter must fill out a customs declaration which includes data on the goods with the assignment of the HS code, foreign trade operation, the owner of the cargo and its buyer. A separate declaration is submitted for each batch of goods. The marks of the customs and border control authorities confirm the legality of the cargo export from the Russian Federation.
- Mandatory payments and duties. Along with filling out and submitting a customs declaration, the law requires mandatory payments: customs duties and customs fees. The rates approved by the legislation are used to calculate the amounts of customs duties; they are harmonized with the WTO rules and have an interface with the ECE trade procedures. Customs duties are calculated individually and include payments for release, storage and escort of cargo by customs authorities.

Therefore, the factors of obtaining the main advantages of export for any small and medium-sized enterprise can be the following:

1. Expansion of the sales market and its ecosystem with future goods of similar profile.

When comparing the number of consumers living in the Russian Federation with potential consumers in foreign markets, the difference is an impressive number of possible buyers. International trade allows Russian producers to sell goods in the world market, where more than seven billion buyers live. Still, their most non-sanction-oriented remain in Africa, the Middle East, the PRC and India [15].

Entering foreign markets is necessary when the size of the domestic market is insufficient and additional marketing efforts of the company bring less marginal revenue.

A unique product or technology or significant technological advantages in a particular area will allow the company to quickly sell products in those foreign markets where they are not widely available. It becomes possible to utilize the potential of foreign markets for the benefit of the enterprise.

2. Expansion of sales volumes and growth of focus group of potential consumers.

If an enterprise has an opportunity to produce products/services in larger quantities than can be realized in the domestic market, the most rational direction of activity is to maximize the use of production capabilities and promote excessive products to foreign markets.

3. Increasing the level of the enterprise, its hierarchy, integration in the structure of the market or in the meso-level of the corresponding cluster or sub-sector.

Export activity gives an opportunity to:

- Expand and specialize latent and explicit competitive advantages of the enterprise;
- Use excessive production capacities at their underutilization (combination of outsourcing and insourcing) if they arose due to a decrease in the level of demand (export allows to reduce unit costs and get additional income in currency);
- Enhance profits by increasing export sales and multiplying its possible substitutes in less developed markets;
- Economies of scale: expanding sales through exports will allow the company to increase its output, potentially localize production, and increase innovation, and thereby reduce unit costs;
- Take advantage of the tax and financial benefits available to exporting enterprises: various national governments actively promote exports of goods. Advantages for enterprises specializing in seasonal products to apply various schemes of guest workers and less skilled labor;
- Equalize seasonal fluctuations in demand by exporting the enterprise to countries where demand for seasonal products falls in other months. For example, northern regions with a long winter cannot fully provide fruits and vegetables all the year round. By exporting seasonal products not possible for other countries due to natural and climatic peculiarities, the enterprise can avoid reduction of sales within the country and create unique products for future seasons of global sales.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Despite the sanctions and growing russophobia of some Western states, Russia, through REC and other mechanisms of export support of Russian companies, should defend its national interests and neither fall into either technological or managerial autarky, nor to allow the global corporatocracy to continue to own some key goods and competencies in Russia itself, thus exposing our state to growing threats and challenges to national security and self-identity, and should support its growing national consciousness and national identity.

The prospects for reorientation of Russian companies' exports under sanctions can be considered from several key perspectives: diversification of markets (creating new sales channels), development of new goods and services (adapting to the needs of buyers), increasing domestic production, cooperation with new partners (including foreign ones), support from the state, development of transport infrastructure (increasing trade with new regions), adaptation to new conditions (in particular, introducing digitalization of the business environment).

Notably, export reorientation also brings risks and challenges such as the need to change business models, adequate risk management, and possible barriers to new markets. Nevertheless, with the right strategy and support, Russian companies can find new opportunities for growth and development in the changed international environment.

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